

SUMMARY OF EVIDENCE TABLE

THE IMPACT OF LIVER DISEASE ON MORTALITY IN CYSTIC FIBROSIS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PROTOCOL

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Summary of Findings Table:

First Author:		Journal:			Year:		Volume (issue):		Pages:		Country	
Title:							Study Design		Study Population		Time Frame	
AIMS							Experimental <input type="checkbox"/> Prognostic Model. <input type="checkbox"/> Observational <input type="checkbox"/> Prospective <input type="checkbox"/> Retrospective <input type="checkbox"/> Cross-Sectional. <input type="checkbox"/> Other. <input type="checkbox"/>		Single Centre. <input type="checkbox"/> National Registry. <input type="checkbox"/> Population based. <input type="checkbox"/> Combination <input type="checkbox"/> Other. <input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Dx CF Sweat < 60mmol/L 2 CFTR mutations Other	
Liver Disease Classification		Other Classification:			Splenomegaly		Exclusion Criteria				Stats	
NACFF. <input type="checkbox"/> European: <input type="checkbox"/> Koh et al <input type="checkbox"/> Colombo <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>		US: Echogenic/homogenous Liver + splenomegaly <input type="checkbox"/> Other US Signs <input type="checkbox"/> Documented histological diagnosis. <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical Examination <input type="checkbox"/> Only evidence of PH <input type="checkbox"/> Other/unclear. <input type="checkbox"/>			Enlarged spleen clinically <input type="checkbox"/> >95 th Centile in Ultrasound <input type="checkbox"/> > 12cms in length <input type="checkbox"/> Other. <input type="checkbox"/>		Other Liver Disease: <input type="checkbox"/> Prior Transplant Liver <input type="checkbox"/> Lung <input type="checkbox"/> L/L <input type="checkbox"/> L/H <input type="checkbox"/> Other. <input type="checkbox"/>				Means ±SD <input type="checkbox"/> Median IQR. <input type="checkbox"/> Kaplan Meier. <input type="checkbox"/> Log Rank. <input type="checkbox"/> Mortality Rate. <input type="checkbox"/> Cox/HR <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>	
Demographics and Risk Factors Included		CFLD	NSCFLD (other classification)	Control No LD	P	Outcome/Mortality		CFLD	NSCFLD (Other)	Controls		P
Total population n						No. Deaths						
No. included in analysis n%						Proportion y (%)						
Age	Under					Person Yrs Fup						
	Over					Duration Yrs Fup						
	All					Survival Rate						
Gender	M					All-Cause Mortality Rate						
						Specific Mortality Rate	Pulmonary					
Genotype	HomoDF508						Liver					
	HeteroDF508					Other						
	Other					Liver Tx n%						
FEV1						Lung Tx n% (L or L/H)						
Height						Liver + Lung Tx n%						
Weight						TIPS n%						
BMI						Age at death						
MI						Risk Factors Mortality						
URSO	Y/N/NR					Age						
CFRD	Y/N/NR					Gender M						
Criteria CFRD	NDDG	WHO	ADA	NR		FEV1						
Comments:						Height						
						Weight						
						BMI						
						CFRD						
						Abn LFT						
						Platelet						
					Other							

Data Dictionary for Summary of Findings:

Variable	Description	Types of data collection
First Author		Text
Journal		Text
Year	Year of publication in Print	Text
Volume (issue)		Text
Pages		Text
Country	Where research was conducted	Text
Title	As published	Text
Aims	As described by authors	Text
Study Design	Identify the study methodology using one if the standard terms included	Drop down list
Study Population	Identify if the study is based on data from a single hospital, a group of hospitals, a national study, or recognised national CF data registries. Particularly identify if the study is based on a combination of the above study populations	Drop down list
Time Frame	Identify the time frame in which the study took place, which may have implications for diagnostic criteria used or management of CFLD	Range of years
Diagnosis of CF	Identify, if reported , the criteria for the diagnosis of CF	Drop down list
Liver Disease Classification NACFF Consensus Report ¹ European Consensus Report ² Koh Adult criteria for CFLD ³ Colombo published criteria in 2002 ⁴ Other	A list of the classification of CFLD which have been proposed over the past 20 years	Drop Down List
Other classifications of CFLD	This category allows for other potential considerations in the diagnosis of CFLD the authors may have used, including requiring evidence of portal hypertension (PH) for a diagnosis of CFLD	Drop down list
Splenomegaly	This seeks to establish the criteria used to diagnose Splenomegaly as a criterion for portal hypertension	Drop down list
Exclusion Criteria	This seeks to identify any criteria which were used to exclude participants from individual studies including other liver	Drop down and free test

	diseases, organ transplantation: liver, lung or combined liver and lung or combined lung and heart transplant.	
Stats	This variable examines what statistical tests the authors reported in their methodology. In the risk of bias the appropriate choice of test will be considered	Drop Down list
Demographics and Risk Factors	Demographics, risk factors for CFLD as well as risk factors for mortality as included. Classification of CFLD into 3 groups is based on the North American and European classifications recognising that many studies will only report data for those with CFLD with or without a comparator group. The classification of CFLD implies clinically significant liver disease. Those studies which only include those with portal hypertension as CFLD are identified. The comparison population are those with no evidence liver disease. If provided data on participants who do not meet the criteria for CFLD, but have non-specific abnormalities (NSCFLD) on US or biochemical investigations will be included.	
CFLD, NSCFLD, NoLD or Control population		
Total population	This refers to the total CF population from whom the study population is drawn e.g. total number of persons with CF (PWCF) attending a single centre or nationally.	Number (assigned as per categories used) or total PWCF for centre
Number included in analysis	What proportion (number and percentage) of the eligible population categorised as CFLD, NSCFLD or NOLD are included in the data analysis	Number and percentage as per categories of liver disease
Age	Including any age stratification e.g. under 10 years, over 18 years	Number as per categories of liver disease
Gender M	Number and percentage of male participants	Number and percentage
Genotype HomoDF508 HeteroDF508 Other	Identify the classification of Genotype used Use Other if Class of Mutation Provided	Number and percentage
FEV1	Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second	Number with no decimal places
Height	Record as SDS If raw data provided note same but cannot be included	Number with 2 decimal places
Weight	Record as SDS If raw data provided note same but cannot be included	Number with 2 decimal places
BMI	Record as SDS for those under 23 years of age. Actual BMI data also accepted	Number with 2 decimal places

MI	Meconium Ileus	Yes/No/Not reported
URSO	The proportion of participants taking URSO. Clinical trials of URSO are an exclusion criteria	Number and percentage
CFRD	Cystic Fibrosis Related Diabetes	Yes/No/Not reported
Criteria CFRD	Identify which criteria are used to diagnose CFLD if reported	WHO, American Diabetes Association, Other, Not Reported
Comments	Identify any deviation from any definition considered above	Free Text
Outcome and Mortality	Classification of CFLD NSCFLD, NoLD as per above	
No of deaths	Extract total number of deaths reported, including deaths from non CF causes.	Number
Proportion of Deaths	Calculate if necessary proportion of deaths in each category of LD	Percentage
Person years of follow-up	As per standard reporting of person years of follow-up	Number with 2 decimal places
Duration Years of Follow-up	Reported in years or months- note if mean with SD and Range or median with IQR or total range of follow-up	Number with 2 decimal places and SD, IQR and/or range
Survival Rate	The proportion of participants alive at the end of follow-up noting the denominator of person years of follow-up or total years of follow-up.	Number with 2 decimal places with denominator (person years of follow-up or as a proportion
All-Cause Mortality Rate	Total number of deaths as a proportion or rate. This will include liver transplants as this is not standard care in all countries	Number with 2 decimal places with denominator of person years of follow-up or a proportion of those alive
Specific Mortality Rate	Deaths due to liver disease respiratory or other as a proportion or rate (person years) Liver related includes acute or chronic liver failure or liver transplant	Number with 2 decimal places with denominator of person years of follow-up or as a proportion
Liver Transplant %	Number and Proportion receiving liver transplant	Number and percentage
Lung Transplant %	Number and Proportion receiving lung or heart-lung transplant	Number and percentage
Liver and Lung	Number and Proportion receiving liver and lung transplant	Number and percentage
TIPs N%	Number and Proportion having a TIPs procedure	Number and percentage
Age at death	Mean /median age at death with SD IQR or Range	Number with 2 decimal places and range
Risk factors for mortality	As for baseline data with the following additional considerations	
Age	Determine what age is a risk factor, age at diagnosis CFLD or Age at death	Hazard Ratio – numeric with confidence interval
Abnormal LFTs	Individual or combined abnormalities of AST,ALT,GTT which are above the upper limit of normal, X 1.5, X 2,x 2.5 ULN	Hazard Ratio – numeric with confidence interval
Platelets	Determine if stratified by Platelet count (Normal, < 150,000, other)	Hazard Ratio – numeric with confidence interval
Other		

Abbreviations

ADA	American Diabetes Association
CFLD	cystic fibrosis liver disease
CFRD	cystic fibrosis related diabetes
FEV ₁	Forced expiratory volume in 1 second
Fup	Follow-up
Gender M	Male Gender
Hetero DF508	Heterozygous F508del-CFTR
HomoDF508	Homozygous F508del-CFTR
MI	Meconium Ileus
NACFF	North American Cystic Fibrosis Foundation
NDDG	National Diabetes Data Group (US)
NOLD	No evidence of liver disease
NR	Not Reported
NSCFLD	Non specific liver disease
PH	Portal Hypertension
SD	Standard deviation
SDS	Standard Deviation Score
TIPS	Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
Tx	Transplant
ULN	Upper limit of normal
US	Ultrasound
WHO	World Health Organisation

References

1. Flass T, Narkewicz MR. Cirrhosis and other liver disease in cystic fibrosis. *J Cyst Fibros* 2013; **12**(2): 116-24.
2. Debray D, Kelly D, Houwen R, Strandvik B, Colombo C. Best practice guidance for the diagnosis and management of cystic fibrosis-associated liver disease. *J Cyst Fibros* 2011; **10** **Suppl 2**: S29-36.
3. Koh C, Sakiani S, Surana P, et al. Adult-onset cystic fibrosis liver disease: Diagnosis and characterization of an underappreciated entity. *Hepatology* 2017; **66**(2): 591-601.
4. Colombo C, Battezzati PM, Crosignani A, et al. Liver disease in cystic fibrosis: A prospective study on incidence, risk factors, and outcome. *Hepatology* 2002; **36**(6): 1374-82.